

Kinetics of Oxidation of β -Methylnaphthalene by Potassium Permanganate

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Kinetic investigation on the oxidation of β -methylnaphthalene by permanganate in aqueous acetic acid is reported. The main product of oxidation is β -naphthaldehyde, which is not oxidised significantly under the experimental conditions chosen. The influence of manganous, fluoride, and pyrophosphate ions indicates unequivocally that permanganate ion is the predominant oxidant and manganese species of lower valence play only a secondary role. A mechanism involving the rapid formation of a manganate ester, which breaks down in a concerted fashion is suggested.

THE oxidation of toluenes by permanganate has been investigated¹. The kinetics of oxidation of β -methylnaphthalene by permanganate in aqueous acetic acid is reported in this note.

Experimental

Pure BDH sample of β -methylnaphthalene (m.p. = 34.4°) was used as such. All other chemicals used were extra-pure samples. The reactions were carried out at 30.0 ± 0.1° in 80% acetic acid, 20% water (v/v) medium, unless otherwise specified. The rate of oxidation was very fast and to make it conveniently measurable a suitable amount of manganous sulphate was added to each reaction mixture. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the gross manganese iodometrically.

Results and Discussion

The products were isolated from the reaction mixture by ether extraction. While the bulk of the product was β -naphthaldehyde (m.p. 59.2°), a trace amount of β -naphthoic acid (m.p. 181°) was also formed. The product did not contain naphthyl alcohol, dinaphthyl and any other related compounds. The aldehyde was characterized and estimated as its semicarbazone (m.p. 245°).

The oxidation of β -naphthaldehyde under the same experimental conditions was carried out. The rate constants are much lower than those for β -methylnaphthalene. At 30°, k_1 for β -methylnaphthalene is $2.27 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1}$ while that for β -naphthaldehyde is $0.41 \times 10^{-8} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with equal substrate concentrations. (0.012 M).

Rate laws: The reaction is first order in oxidant as well as in substrate, the overall order being two

(Table 1). The activation parameters were evaluated by following the reaction at different temperatures.

$$\Delta H^* = 13.5 \text{ kcal mole}^{-1}, \Delta S^* = -33.6 \text{ e.u. and}$$

$$\Delta F^* = 23.7 \text{ kcal mole}^{-1} (30^\circ).$$

TABLE 1—ORDER OF REACTION

[MnSO ₄] = 0.001 M			
[Oxidant] M	[S] M	$k_1 \times 10^8 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1/[S]$
β -methylnaphthalene			
0.002	0.006	1.39	0.23
0.002	0.008	1.62	0.21
0.002	0.010	2.00	0.20
0.002	0.012	2.27	0.19
0.003	0.012	2.40	0.20
α -methylnaphthalene			
0.001	0.050	2.08	
0.002	0.050	2.02	
0.002	0.080	1.44	
0.002	0.012	0.51	

Effect of Mn(II) ions: In permanganate oxidations a characteristic feature is the possibility of concurrent involvement of more than one manganese species as oxidants². However, for a particular reaction, depending upon the experimental conditions, one of the manganese species may be the predominant oxidant.

A diagnostic test for the predominant involvement of MnO_4^- over other species is the impedance in rate when manganous ions are added to the reaction medium. Manganous ions decrease the concentration of permanganate ion by reaction with it and producing intermediate valence species⁸. On the other hand if any of the intermediate valence states and not permanganate is the main oxidant, Mn(II) would accelerate the reaction. In this study a sharp decrease in rate constant is noticed even when small amounts of manganous sulphate are added to the reaction medium (Table 2). This indicates that MnO_4^- is the primary oxidant.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF COMPLEXING AGENTS

[S]=0.002 M ; Oxidant]=0.0004 M						
[Pyrophosphate] M	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	3.37	3.12	2.69	1.95	1.43	
[KF] M	0.02	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.10
$k_1 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.121	0.059	0.054	0.052	0.047	0.038
[S]=0.01 M ; [Oxidant]=0.002 M						
[MnSO_4] M	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.006
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.91	1.50	1.03	0.92	0.81	0.39

Effect of pyrophosphate and fluoride ions : These two ions are known to complex with Mn(III) and Mn(IV)⁸. Such complexation causes reduction in the concentration of active Mn(III) and Mn(IV). Besides, complexation obliterates the oxidising capacity of intermediate manganese ions. Therefore the effect of these complexing agents is indicative of the importance of intermediate manganese ions in the oxidation. In this study these two complexing agents influence the reaction in a parallel fashion (Table 2). The introduction of these decreases the rate thereby implying that other than permanganate, manganese ions of lower valence, viz. Mn(III) and (IV) are involved in oxidation. However, the rate of the reaction is appreciable even when these complexing agents are present in large concentrations compared to $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$. Thus the inability of these complexing agents to suppress the reaction completely indicates unequivocally that the intermediate manganese species are not the dominant and only oxidants in this reaction.

Effect of solvent : The effect of solvent was investigated in the range 70-90% acetic acid ; below 70% acetic acid the substrate is insoluble while above

90% acetic acid the oxidant is insoluble. With increase in acetic acid content of the medium a small decrease in rate constant was observed (Table 3). This is as expected for a reaction between a neutral molecule and an ion. Besides, it is likely that the variation in acetic acid content of the reaction medium alters the redox potential of the manganese-systems in a manner to reduce the oxidising capacity of the active oxidant. It is well established that redox potentials are sensitive to changes in medium.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT

[S]=0.006 M ; [Oxidant]=0.002 M ; [MnSO_4]=0.001 M ;				
% AcOH - H_2O (v/v)	70-30	75-25	80-20	85-15
$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.55	1.52	1.49	1.41

Relative rates of oxidations of α -methyl-naphthalene and β -methyl-naphthalene : Under identical experimental conditions the α -isomer is much slowly oxidised than the β -isomer (Table 1).

Mechanism : The difficulty in identifying the active oxidant species and the participation of more than one oxidant entity in the reaction are two characteristic problems in proposing mechanisms for permanganate oxidations. Since the results of this study indicate MnO_4^- to be the main oxidant, a tentative mechanism as shown in Scheme 1 may be suggested for the oxidation of β -methyl-naphthalene to β -naphthaldehyde.

Scheme 1

The initial step is assumed to involve the rapid formation of a manganate ester, which breaks down in the rate-controlling step involving a concerted mechanism and producing β -naphthaldehyde and Mn(III) species. The Mn(III) species thus formed can be lost due to either its involvement in further oxidation or disproportionation to Mn(II) and Mn(IV). Such manganate esters were proved to be intermediates in the oxidation of alkanes⁹. The high negative entropy of activation supports such a mechanism.

References

1. C. F. CULLIS and J. W. LADBURY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 555.
2. K. B. WIBERG, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry" Part A (Academic Press, New York, 1965, 39.
3. W. A. WATERS, *Quart. Rev.*, 12, 277.